

DigiVet - Digitalisation of livestock data to improve veterinary public health

WP1 - Deliverable 1.3 - Sweden Swedish stakeholder workshops

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ABBREVIATIONS

AMR – Antimicrobial Resistance
AMU – Antimicrobial Use
API – Application Programming Interface
ASF – African Swine Fever
CS – Case Study
DDDvet – Defined Daily Dose
DCDvet – Defined Course Dose
EMA – European Medicines Agency
EU – European Union
GDPR – The General Data Protection Regulation
LRF - Lantbrukarnas Riksförbund (The Federation of Swedish Farmers)
SBA – The Swedish Board of Agriculture
SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute
STEEP – Societal, Technological, Environmental, Economic, Political
SVA – The National Veterinary Institute of Sweden
WB – Wild Boar
WP – Work Package

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INTRODUCTION

The DigiVet project – “Digitalisation of livestock data to improve veterinary public health”, funded by NordForsk, is a three-year project running between 2021 – 2023, involving the countries UK, Denmark, Sweden, Norway and Estonia. DigiVet is composed of three work packages (WP), where the first, WP1, will investigate the current opportunities, investments, and challenges regarding digitalisation of livestock data. The project also consists of three different case studies (CS). CS1 is about food safety, with particular emphasis on *Salmonella*, CS2 is about health security with focus on antimicrobial use (AMU), and CS3 concerns economic security focusing on transboundary spread of African Swine Fever (ASF).

This report is the Swedish sub report of deliverable 1.3 in DigiVet, within task 1.3 “Stakeholders perception of current challenges/opportunities and knowledge gaps” (WP1). As part of the task, workshops with stakeholders were planned for all CS:s. After the start of the project, such stakeholder discussions have also been ongoing in other projects related to DigiVet. Based on our assessment, performing similar workshops on the same topic and with the same stakeholders would not constitute responsible use of resources. In fact, it might even damage the motivation to further contribute to the collaboration on the CS specific topics. Therefore, most focus was put on the AMU CS, where an increasing need of stakeholder dialogue was noted (due to new European legislation to report AMU, and the construction of a new system for acquiring and maintaining AMU-data). For the Salmonella CS, the project was able to collaborate and retrieve material from workshops in two Government Assignments; one on revision of the Swedish salmonella control system, and one on the risk of introduction and spread of zoonotic diseases. Reports from these assignment and workshops have already been published¹. The results related to digitalisation, data management and use have been summarised in this report. For the ASF CS, Swedish input has been limited to participation in stakeholder discussion within an on-going networking initiative (“KrisGIS” – use of GIS for crisis preparedness and management) by the Swedish Civil Contingencies Agency, as this initiative relates to data sources relevant for the Swedish perspective on the ASF CS. Activities within KrisGIS are ongoing and results from seminars and workshops have not been published. In this report, we only give a brief summary of the content and conclusions made so far. The various workshops explored current use of digital data as well as challenges and opportunities in data digitalisation. The results are divided into three chapters in this report, one chapter per CS.

A full introduction to this deliverable is given in the report “DigiVet – UK Stakeholder Workshop”, the main report of the deliverable 1.3. More information and other deliverables from the DigiVet project can be found at the following link: <https://zenodo.org/communities/digivet/>.

¹ Reports with more results from the assignments and workshops, relevant for the Salmonella CS, can be found at the following links: <https://www.sva.se/media/h4zkoong/sva-f%C3%B6rstudie-om-%C3%A5tg%C3%A4rder-mot-salmonella-hos-lantbrukets-djur.pdf> and <https://zenodo.org/record/7385314>

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The theoretical framework used as a basis for the workshops is explained in more detail in the DigiVet deliverable 1.2². The framework was adapted from Zhang et al. (2022), defining different components of the data lifecycle (Figure 1). Challenges and opportunities to digitalise data and finding new technical solutions in relation to the data lifecycle were investigated from societal, technological, environmental, economic, and political (STEEP) perspectives.

Figure 1 - The data lifecycle, adapted from Zhang et al. (2022)

² Deliverable 1.2 is published at: <https://zenodo.org/record/7440884>

1 CHAPTER 1 – CS1 FOOD SAFETY: SALMONELLA

1.1 INTRODUCTION

Workshops were held within the framework of two government assignments: one regarding a revision of the Swedish salmonella control programme and one regarding the probability of introducing new potentially zoonotic agents into Swedish animal production. The workshop within the salmonella assignment was held using the system thinking technique with the aim to map and characterize the direct and indirect dependence between stakeholders within the present control program and during and following the revision of the programme. The aim of the workshop within the zoonosis assignment was to illustrate and map the complex network of responsibilities and communication between stakeholders within the zoonosis field in Sweden with the goal to identify areas of improvement and identify data sources.

1.2 IDENTIFICATION OF STAKEHOLDERS

For the salmonella workshop a stakeholder analysis was performed to identify relevant stakeholders to invite. A core group was formed with representatives from the National Veterinary Institute (SVA), the Public Health Agency of Sweden, the Swedish Board of Agriculture (SBA), and the Swedish Food Agency, consisting of six people in total. A Mendelow Matrix was used to categorize the stakeholders, only stakeholders that ended up as having both a high interest and high power were invited to the workshop. It was decided not to invite more than 25-30 people to be able to have discussions with the whole group.

In addition to the core group, representatives from the following organizations were invited:

- Lantbrukarnas Riksförbund (LRF) – The Federation of Swedish Farmers
- Gård & Djurhälsan – Farm & Animal Health
- Växa Sverige – Cattle farmers association (henceforth called Växa)
- Distriktsveterinärerna – District veterinarians
- Svenska köttföretagen – Swedish Meat Enterprises
- County veterinary officers from four different counties
- County medical officer

In total, there were 23 participants from 11 different organizations/authorities at the workshop.

In the zoonosis workshop, in addition to the stakeholders listed above, the Swedish Work Environment Authority and a representative for one Swedish municipality participated.

1.3 DEFINING DATA AND DATA SHARING

All bacteriological findings of salmonella in feed, animals, humans and food are notifiable in Sweden, and therefore data on this is collected and recorded. In addition to clinical surveillance there are continuous active surveillance components and scheduled sampling within the control programme (Figure 2). There are also repeated serological surveillance activities performed. Data from all these activities is compiled yearly in the report “Surveillance of infectious diseases in animals and humans in Sweden 20XX”³. The report is produced jointly by the authorities responsible for the different parts of the food chain. Some of these data on salmonella are also

³ The report is published every year, earlier reports can be downloaded from:
<https://www.sva.se/amnesomraden/smittlage/sjukdomsrapporter-om-sva-s-overvakning/>

reported to EFSA. No denominator data is reported for livestock, except for the surveillance at slaughterhouses and for the mandatory sampling in poultry flocks.

Scheduled sampling

One of the outcomes of the zoonosis assignment workshop was that registers are kept by many different stakeholders and that there is limited or no sharing of data between stakeholders from the registers. Several of the registers are poorly updated and only very limited quality control of data is performed.

Sampling upon disease suspicion

A big challenge when sharing data between agencies, and from private organisations to agencies is the legal aspect. Sharing between agencies can be obstructed by confidentiality in data which requires complicated legal agreements. Private organisations might be concerned to share some data with agencies due to the Swedish Act of Public Access to Information and Secrecy or the Archives Act. Other laws, such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) may also need to be considered.

Voluntary programmes

An outcome from the zoonosis workshop was that there is a common understanding that if data sharing between authorities involved in the food chain would be enabled without the limitations mentioned above it would strengthen and provide new opportunities for the disease control and food safety work along the food chain.

Sampling following a confirmed case

Figure 2 - Schematic presentation of the sampling in the Swedish salmonella control programme.

2 CHAPTER 2 – CS2 HEALTH SECURITY: ANTIMICROBIAL USE

2.1 INTRODUCTION

In this chapter we describe the design and results of the Swedish stakeholder workshop that focused on data regarding AMU.

The more specific formulated aims of this workshop were:

- Investigate the needs and purposes of using AMU-data, from different stakeholders' perspectives.
- Identify opportunities and challenges to digitalise these data and increase availability.
- To provide a basis for developing examples or prototypes within the DigiVet project, to make this data more accessible, summarize it and present it (for example through dashboards) to increase return value to agencies, decision makers and other stakeholders.

2.2 WORKSHOP PARTICIPANTS AND SESSIONS

National stakeholder agencies and organisations working with AMU-data in the veterinary sector (primarily data reported by veterinarians or animal owners through journals) were invited to participate in this workshop. The invited participants were from SVA, SBA and animal health organisations in the private sector: Växa and Farm & Animal Health.

The workshop was held at SVA in Swedish, during an afternoon in the autumn 2022, and included the following steps:

- **Introduction to DigiVet and the workshop**

The hosts at SVA welcomed the participants and gave an introduction to DigiVet, and the agenda and guidelines for the workshop. All participants introduced themselves to each other.

- **Definition of Swedish AMU-data**

A discussion in the big group where the stakeholders discussed what data we include when we talk about AMU-data.

- **Identification of stakeholders**

The data lifecycle (a simplified version of Figure 1) was presented to the participants and stakeholders were identified throughout the data lifecycle and their role at each step. This was done in the big group, where the participants could place post-it notes on the data lifecycle while discussing.

- **Identifying the purpose to use AMU-data**

Identifying the purpose to use AMU-data per key stakeholder. This was done in three smaller groups: one for SVA, one for SBA, and one for Växa together with Farm & Animal Health. Each group identified their own purposes.

- **Sketching solutions (dashboards)**

Sketching of data analysis and visualization (dashboards) tools to increase return value to each of the stakeholders and improve basis for decision making, more specifically to fulfil the identified purposes (from the previous session). These discussions were held in two groups with mixed participants.

- **Challenges and opportunities to achieve solutions**

Societal, technological, environmental, economic, and political (STEEP) challenges and opportunities to strengthen digitalisation and to enable the building of the tool were discussed in the big group. The identified challenges and opportunities were after the workshop mapped in relation to the data life cycle.

The steps above that were carried out in smaller groups were also followed by discussions in the whole group. This report was written based only on the discussions in the big group. All participants were given the opportunity to read and comment on this report.

2.3 RESULTS

9 participants attended, representing all invited agencies and organisations. Participants were mainly veterinarians and epidemiologists working with AMU-data in different ways and one participant had more technical knowledge of data engineering. One participant joined digitally and could participate in almost all moments.

2.3.1 Defining Swedish AMU data

In Sweden antimicrobials are mainly used by veterinarians at their clinics or at the farm, or by animal owners through prescriptions from the veterinarians. Veterinarians buy antimicrobial products at pharmacies through requisition and animal owner buy these products from pharmacies through prescription. If the veterinarian initiates treatment during a visit at the farm, he or she may leave veterinary medicines for follow up treatment. For animal species or production types where prescription largely dominates (commercial pig production, dogs, cats), the prescription sales from pharmacies are assumed to be a good proxy for use. On the other hand, data from requisition sales does not tell how much medical products are used at a certain time or which animal is treated. To monitor this part of AMU Sweden relies on records from veterinarians (the veterinarian is responsible for reporting even if the animal owner continues to carry out the treatment initiated from the veterinarian). Veterinarians are obliged to report this, according to recent legislation. The acquisition and maintenance of this data is done by SBA, and a new system for this is currently under construction (when the workshop was carried out, in autumn 2022), to among other things improve data acquisition and data quality.

The participants together decided to limit the workshop to focus on AMU-data for pig and cattle.

2.3.2 Identification of stakeholders throughout the data life cycle

Table 1 shows the stakeholders that were identified during the workshop, for each step in the data lifecycle. Important to note is that it was not obvious to the participants during the workshop what the second and third step meant ("Data aggregation & processing" and "Data management & maintenance"). But after some discussion we agreed that these steps mainly represented data processing in a data warehouse from raw data to a format on which the data is stored and maintained within the data warehouse. However, the processed data can also be stored and maintained by other external parties that are not the main responsible agencies.

The data acquisition of AMU-data is mainly done by clinical veterinarians through different journal systems or directly to a web-based tool at SBA. SBA is the responsible authority, and involved in gathering, processing, managing, and maintaining data from the records They also make decisions on what information needs to be collected in the journal systems (based on legal requirements and

regulations). SVA has been involved as a consulting partner in this work. The Swedish eHealth Agency is responsible for the data of sales collected at the pharmacies, both sales to veterinarians as well as prescription sales to animal owners (both data acquisition, processing, management, and maintenance). The Swedish Medical Products Agency have databases on medical products.

The data on use (from medical records) stored at SBA and sales from pharmacies stored at The Swedish eHealth Agency have been shared with SVA and Växa (to Växa only aggregated or non-confidential parts of the data) who also work with and store this data (possibly also other stakeholders). Both SVA and Växa analyse this data (SVA has mainly analysed sales data) and do also combine this data with other data sources. Who will have access to medical records will change in the future due to legislation. SBA, SVA as well as Växa have been involved in producing various yearly reports on antimicrobial sales and reported use⁴, which is one outcome of the data usage. More stakeholders were also identified as users of the data, e.g. animal owners, Farm & Animal Health, researchers, EU and more (see Table 1). Data usage can for example involve data processing, aggregation, merging with other datasets, calculations, analyses and visualisations. The return value of the data reaches a broader audience as many parties are interested in the Swedish AMU (see Table 1 for all identified stakeholders at the step of return value). During this moment it was also brought up that farmers usually are not that interested in using or seeing AMU-data. It can also be perceived as a very sensitive topic as the farmers usually are very careful and restrictive in their use of antimicrobials.

Table 1 – Identified stakeholders to AMU-data throughout the data life cycle

Data acquisition	Data aggregation & processing	Data management & maintenance	Data usage	Return value
Animal owners	SBA	SBA	Animal owners	Animal owners
Clinical veterinarians	Swedish eHealth Agency	SVA	County Administrative Boards	Clinical veterinarians
Owners of medical record systems		Swedish eHealth Agency	EU	District veterinarians
Pharmacies		Växa	European Medicines Agency (EMA)	EMA
SBA			Researchers	EU
SVA			SBA	Farms
Swedish eHealth Agency			SVA	Opinion leaders
Swedish Medical Products Agency			Swedish eHealth Agency	Other providers of education
			The Federation of Swedish Farmers	Politicians
			The industry organisation for Swedish pig farmers	SVA
			Veterinary organisations (e.g. Växa, Farm & Animal Health)	Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences
				The Federation of Swedish Farmers
				The industry organisation for Swedish pig farmers
				The public
				The retail sector (food)
				Veterinary organisations (e.g. Växa, Farm & Animal Health, Lunden's Animal Health)

⁴ Examples of yearly reports are "Swedres-Svarm" from SVA and other agencies, and "Antibiotikastatistik" from Växa.

2.3.3 Identification of the purpose to use AMU-data

2.3.3.1 Växa and Farm & Animal Health

Växa and Farm & Animal Health identified the following purposes for them to use AMU-data:

- Follow up general work with animal health and welfare
- Education of veterinarians and animal owners
- Feedback and benchmarking of AMU to animal owners
- Show data of the “non-use” or cases where antimicrobials are not used/underused
- Added value to Swedish farmers

Växa and Farm & Animal Health work to improve animal health and welfare at farms. Analysing AMU-data can give insights about the current and past health situation and can help them follow up their work, for example they calculate quality indicators such as the proportion of diagnosed infections that are treated with penicillin (other diagnosis and treatments that are not antimicrobials is also important for this, but outside the scope of this workshop). Knowledge and statistics from AMU-data is also used in education of veterinarians and animal owners. For this they would like to show AMU per county, type of antimicrobial and disease. Data could also be used to give feedback and benchmarking of the AMU on a farm level. It is however not clear if, or how, the farmers would like to see their data, and it could be very sensitive to share individual farm data. Växa and Farm & Animal health would also like to show when AMU is not used, as there is a risk that farmers or veterinarians choose not to treat animals because they are afraid of using antimicrobials, which can lead to animal health and welfare issues. It would be useful to see “non-use” or use in relation to disease. But one problem with that is that we do not have data on actual diseases, but only diagnosed diseases. The AMU-data can also give added value to Swedish farmers as the AMU on Swedish farms is relatively low and we only treat diseased animals.

2.3.3.2 SBA

SBA identified the following purposes to use AMU-data, from SBA’s perspective:

- Reporting to EMA
- Surveillance of animal health situation
- Surveillance of AMU
- Share data with other agencies, interest organizations, researchers etc.
- Share data and information with the county administrative boards to perform risk-based inspections (of AMU, conducted by veterinarian at farm level)
- Reporting to the Swedish government
- As support in decision making and when writing regulations at SBA. Data is also used for follow-up and to evaluate the effect of decisions.

SBA is an agency and must fulfil their mission from the government. The identified purposes are within this mission. From 2023 SBA is responsible for reporting the AMU to EMA, which is why a new system for collecting and storing AMU-data is currently constructed, to fulfil the requirements for this reporting.

2.3.3.3 SVA

SVA identified the following purposes to use AMU-data, from SVA’s perspective:

- Support work for rational (responsible) AMU
- Putting occurrence of antimicrobial resistance (AMR) (in animals and food) in relation/connection to AMU

- Disease surveillance (for some diseases AMU can be used as a proxy-indicator)
- To answer queries internally and from other agencies and organizations

In SVA:s instructions from the Government, it is specified that SVA shall a) monitor and analyse AMR in bacteria from animals and food; and b) support work for rational use of antimicrobials. To analyse trends in AMR, it is important to understand the connection between AMU and AMR and monitor this in parallel. To work for a more responsible AMU, it is also important to follow trends and to develop indicators. For both these purposes, SVA also work on how to measure AMU, as this could be done using various units of measurement. The unit of measurement best suited for a particular situation should be used, and to use national units may be preferable for certain situations. SVA also performs research to support the identified purposes.

2.3.4 Finding solutions

A visualisation tool to fulfil the identified purposes of using AMU-data should, according to the first discussion group, provide the user with choices of which parameters to show, filter or aggregate by, and type of visualisation (e.g. a bar plot, line plot, circle diagram, maps etc.). The user should for example be able to filter by animal type, category of medical product, reason for treatment, units of measure, age and sex of animal and time period. They should also be able to choose on what time scale (per day, month etc.) and on what geographical level (per municipality, county, country, etc.) to aggregate the data.

The target group for this dashboard would be broad and potentially include many of the stakeholders. As they discussed it, it would mainly be on a national scale, but it could also be adapted to show farm level data for veterinarians and animal owners. The choices and levels of details should be adapted for different users due to confidentiality in data. Farm level data for example is sensitive and should (in cases when the farm is identifiable) probably only be accessible by the farmer, or at least for the farmer to decide.

A comment to this idea was that many users do not want to have too many options, or make the decisions themselves, on what to view. It could also be hard to know what is important to look at. To solve this, the dashboard could have predefined designs for different target groups and stakeholders, but still with the opportunity to change filters, aggregation levels and diagram types.

The second group also suggested that the user should be able to make a lot of own choices on what to display, such as being able to choose from units of measurement. They wanted the tool to display AMU in relation to others (such as other farms, veterinarians, regions, etc.), at a certain time but also over time. The user should also be able to choose whether to show AMU per organ-system or diagnosis (on a rough level), per medical product (confidential) or at least per substance or class of medical product, per administration method (e.g. injection, oral, local treatment, etc.) or per animal age and sex. It would also be valuable to be able to connect the AMU-data to data on diseases. In the best scenario all these data exist at one place, where the stakeholders could extract the desired or allowed data (in the most detailed format or aggregated and filtered) but also have a tool for analysis and visualisations.

A comment to the second group was that few users would be interested in so detailed data (such as AMU per organ-system or administration method), especially not farmers or veterinarians. But for decision making and other work at agencies it would be more relevant. In general, it would also be very important that the tool is pedagogical and easy to use. Some users may find it hard to interpret

the data, and there is a risk of misinterpretations. The tool should therefore contain help to make the right interpretations and advice on how to use it.

2.3.5 Opportunities and challenges to achieve the discussed solutions

Five challenges or opportunities were identified, that need to be addressed to achieve the solutions discussed in the previous section (visualisation and data analytics tools). These are mapped in relation to the data lifecycle in Table 2.

Table 2 – Identified challenges and opportunities in relation to the data life cycle, to achieve solutions discussed in previous section.

Data acquisition	Data aggregation & processing	Data management & maintenance	Data usage	Return value
Data quality		Technical solutions of data sharing between agencies and organisation	Which units of measure to use <hr/> Legal issues <hr/> Manual work with data	

2.3.5.1 Data quality

Quality of data reported by veterinarians, at least the data reported through record systems or by e-services, has been poor. Firstly, much data has been missing due to lack of reporting, and secondly, the systems of reporting have not been robust enough to collect data of good quality (for example it has not been obvious how to report the amount of used medical products, and information whether an entry describes prescription or actual use has not been clear). The transfer between record systems and SBA, where data is stored and maintained, has also in some cases been problematic and some information has been lost along the way.

The new system that is being developed by SBA (to fulfil new requirements to report AMU, based on new EU legislation) is a big opportunity to improve data quality during acquisition and further down the data life cycle (the first version of the new system was finished in February 2023, after this report was initially written). Still there will be a need to validate that the data corresponds with actual AMU and to assure the data quality from farm to database. The stakeholders could help each other with this as it is of interest to everyone.

It was brought up that there could maybe be a risk of underreporting if veterinarians and animal owners can compare their AMU with others. Sanctions were mentioned as a possible solution to this and to improve reporting quality (which was made possible through legislation, from April 2023, after this report was initially written). Increased return value to the animal owners and veterinarians that acquire data can also increase the data quality, for example if they are able to see their data as visualisations.

2.3.5.2 Data sharing – technical solutions

To be able to build technical solutions, such as a dashboard, one important prerequisite is to have simple continuous data sharing between agencies and organisation. For example, data needs to be shared between journal systems and SBA, between the Swedish eHealth Agency, SBA and SVA, SBA. Some aggregated data may also be shared with Växa and Farm & Animal health or other stakeholders. Data sharing is needed for example to make calculations and analyses that are based on various data sources from different stakeholders, which is often the case for AMU-data, or if one agency is to build a comprehensive solution. It is also necessary to share data in a secure and robust manner.

Application programming interfaces (API) is a good opportunity to address this challenge. These API:s do not need to be open but should allow external access by approved users. To store data in servers hosted by external companies may not be considered a secure solution so one option could be that some Swedish agencies build a common technical solution for this. It could also be beneficial if different systems for handling data are able to communicate somehow, for example SBA:s system to handle AMU-data and the project “Agronod” – which is a digital platform to enable and improve sharing of farm data between farms and organisations. Maybe data could be shared between these systems as well.

2.3.5.3 Units of measurement

It is not obvious which units of measurement should be used to represent the AMU. For example, the measure could be weight of used active antimicrobial substances in total numbers, or per some denominator. We could calculate use per animal, per animal at risk, per slaughtered animal and in that case, should we count the number of animals or the weight of slaughtered animals? For this we would also need number of animals per farm which is another data source and requires more reporting from the farmers. This data is collected today by SBA, but it also comes with challenges.

If the longer-term goal of monitoring AMU is to have a more responsible AMU to decrease AMR, it is not always equal to decrease the AMU. It is important to know which antimicrobials are used, during how long time and in what cases they are used. Some antimicrobials are more potent, meaning that less amount is needed, but the risk of AMR to these substances, should it spread, can be higher. To understand this better we might need other measurements, or to have various measurements for different purposes and to compare AMU on different levels. This also implies higher demands when acquiring data.

EMA has proposed dose corrected measures to monitor and follow up the AMU at animal species level (defined daily dose: “DDDvet” and defined course dose: “DCDvet”). These measures are often disadvantageous for Sweden in a country comparison according to the participants. It would be good if Sweden together with other Nordic countries could develop better measures to add some nuance to current measure, and to improve comparisons and the work on a more responsible AMR.

It is not obvious how to solve this challenge and will require a lot of intellectual work.

2.3.5.4 Legal issues

A big challenge when sharing data between agencies, and from private organisations to agencies is the legal aspect. Sharing between agencies can be obstructed by confidentiality in data which requires complicated legal agreements. Private organisations might be concerned to share some data with agencies due to the Swedish Act of Public Access to Information and Secrecy or the Archives Act. Other laws, such as GDPR may also need to be considered when building these solutions. This was however not discussed further during the workshop but needs to be addressed.

2.3.5.5 Manual work with data

Currently quite a lot of manual work is done to do calculations and analyses from the AMU-data. For example, Växa do manual work when they combine AMU-data with production data from dairy cows at farm level to construct reports and visualisations, and SVA do a lot of manual work in excel while working with AMU-data. The new system to acquire and maintain AMU-data that is developed at SBA is an opportunity to enable more digitalised data flows and data processing which

can lower the risk of human errors, decrease double work, and enable use of common indicators and measures. But to automatize this work it is important to understand what is done manually. It is also important to understand the data, quality, possible bias in the data and so on, so experts should be involved when digitalising processes for example when using data for decision making and when making interpretations.

2.3.6 Take home message from the workshop

To summarize the workshop, some key points that were brought up were:

- Technical solutions are probably not the biggest challenge, but rather data quality in the acquisition and legal issues concerning sharing data.
- The importance of return value to veterinarians and animal owners to improve data quality. To increase the return value, it is important to understand what measures and tools could be useful for these stakeholders.
- The importance of using common and useful measures to monitor AMU, different for various purposes, to make better comparisons and to improve decision making.

2.4 DISCUSSION

Depending on the stakeholder, the AMU-data can be used for various purposes. In a broader perspective it often comes down to better understand the AMU and to understand how it is connected to AMR, in order to make decisions on different levels (animal owners and veterinarians on farm level, but also decisions on legislation on national and international levels). This is important to achieve a more responsible use of antimicrobials, to secure animal and human health and welfare.

There are various opportunities and challenges to digitalise AMU-data and workflows to increase availability and return value. The data quality has been a big challenge in the old systems to collect data on AMU, but currently digitalisation processes are ongoing (i.e. the new system built by SBA, for acquiring and maintaining data). This can contribute to overcome some of the challenges with for example data quality, enhance technical solutions for data sharing between stakeholders, and improve data processing and analysis to better monitor AMU. It can also contribute to less manual work which can decrease risk of human mistakes in the workflows. Data quality will also depend on the level of reporting, so it would be important to increase the incentives for veterinarians, and in some cases animal owners, to report the AMU. This could for example be done either by better legislation and control, but also through better return value from the data to these stakeholders. For this purpose, it would be important to understand what data veterinarians and animal owners would benefit from and be interested in. This in turn could hopefully also lead to improved and more responsible AMU.

To choose which units of measurements to use is still a challenge, and some metrics might need to be adapted for different circumstances, such as national differences. Digitalised data and workflows could make it easier to perform calculations of various measures, so that different units can be used depending on situations and purposes. The new legislation from EU to report AMU can hopefully contribute to speed up the development of digital workflows further which could also enable better comparisons between countries and drive the development of units to measure AMU.

Although some parts of the data lifecycle might be improved with the new system for collecting AMU-data, there are still important solutions to be built to monitor the AMU and make the

solutions available for the right stakeholders and decision makers. A dashboard is one example of a solution to monitor AMU, but not necessarily the best one. Either way, the challenges are not mainly technical, but rather about allocating resources and responsibilities, from an economic and political perspective. Legislation can be a barrier when it comes to sharing data and access systems to monitor AMU, but legislation could also drive the processes to improve digitalisation through the whole data lifecycle.

In conclusion, digitalisation of AMU-data is one important factor to better understand how antimicrobials are used and how we can achieve a more responsible use, to decrease the occurrence of resistant microorganisms.

3 CHAPTER 3 – CS3 ECONOMIC SECURITY: AFRICAN SWINE FEVER

3.1 BACKGROUND

ASF has emerged in European wild boar (WB) and possesses a major threat to the pig industry. Because there is no effective vaccine and the mortality rate is high, preventing outbreaks is critical for animal health and welfare and to prevent economic losses in the pork industry. Also, from a Swedish perspective, the risk for the introduction of ASF is a reality today. Infected meat (e.g., ham or sausage) originating from infected pigs or WB in affected countries, and which is thrown in the environment at reach for hungry WB, is considered the most likely route for ASF to be introduced and spread in Sweden. Lessons learned from affected countries in the EU suggest that early detection of the disease is crucial if this happens, but also that preventive actions are needed in order to allow for successful control. However, to be efficient, feasible and sustainable, such measures must be targeted towards regions at risk. Moreover, they must also be based on up-to-date geodata from various sources such as environmental, climatic, topographic and traffic data mainly from the Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute (SMHI), the Swedish mapping, cadastral and land registration authority (Lantmäteriet), the Swedish Transport Administration (Trafikverket), and the European Union's Earth Observation Programme (Copernicus).

3.2 WORKSHOP INSIGHTS ABOUT DATA CHALLENGES

To learn more about geodata provided by various actors, a representative from SVA has attended workshops (under the name “KrisGIS”), given by the Swedish Civil Contingencies Agency, about geodata and maps in crisis preparedness. The purpose of KrisGIS is to create the conditions for the actors to collaborate effectively and quickly on GIS issues in structured way in the event of a crisis. A reflection from these workshops is that there are several challenges to share data between various actors, both technical and legal. Another challenge is to have knowledge of what data are available from different actors.

DISCUSSION

One common challenge that was brought up in all workshops was sharing data between different stakeholders, both agencies and private organisations. This challenge is often due to legal barriers, but could also be technical. Challenges with data quality was also discussed, which could be an issue in various stages of the data life cycle, firstly in the acquisition phase, but also when processing or using data. To improve data quality, it could be important for the people acquiring data to understand the importance of the data and how it is used, but also to provide good return values and incentives to them. To keep good data quality along the life cycle it would also be important to have good technical solutions to process and maintain data, as well as for sharing data. Manual work, for example for calculations and analyses, can also be a problem for data quality. Humans can make errors and manual work can be more person dependent than if the workflows are digitalised and automated, it is important however that experts should verify and secure the quality of automated workflows.

Digitalisation of data and workflows provide opportunities to improve data quality, remove manual steps, and to share data in a more secure way. However, legal barriers will still remain a challenge. Digitalisation of public and animal health data will also require investments and it needs to be clear which actors or agencies should be responsible for different parts. If the challenges are overcome, data of good quality could become more accessible (directly or through tools providing decision support and better understanding of data) for the relevant stakeholders and decision makers and ultimately lead to improved disease control to increase food safety as well as health and economic security.